

ROLE OF E-BANKING SERVICE WITH CUSTOMER PERCEPTION AND SATISFACTION IN ONGOING SCENARIO

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Abstract:

Many new techniques are being developed today that are expected to create a competitive environment. Every bank seeks to build long-term relationships with its customers to increase revenue, develop loyalty, build resistance to unfavourable branding, and minimize price sensitivity. The ultimate purpose of any organization is profit generation, which can be achieved through customer perception and satisfaction. A happy consumer will come back and suggest e-banking services to others, resulting in increased sales and profits. Banks are no exception, because they also live from profit. Customer perception and satisfaction are the basic requirements for customer retention and loyalty and thus contribute to the achievement of economic goals. Banks are gradually diversifying their operations by offering both online and traditional banking. Internet banking is only an addition to classic branch banking. The main objective of this study was to examine the customers' perceptions towards the e-banking services of the selected banks and to examine the level of customers' satisfaction with the banks' e-banking services. 220 respondents were identified to measure customer satisfaction related to the adoption of technology-enabled banking self-services using a survey methodology. A ranking technique is used to determine the level of customer satisfaction with banks' e-banking services. The consumer expects a high level of satisfaction as customer expectations of electronic banking are quite high and competition is fierce with little variety in the types of services offered. As a result, bankers have recognized the critical nature of customer satisfaction in online banking.

Keywords: e-banking; Service quality; customer satisfaction; Customer Relationship and Indian Banking Sector.

Introduction:

Banks are ingrained in every aspect of economic life. The growth and development of any economy depends to a large extent on the functioning of its financial institutions. A sound banking system mobilizes public money and makes it available for a variety of investment purposes. Banks are regarded as the engines of economic development and prosperity in the

country. Modern trade and commerce are totally dependent on these financial services. Banking services have now spread to all parts of the nation. In this regard, banks serve as a channel to drive a country's economic growth. Banking has also become an integral part of people's everyday lives. Human existence is inextricably linked to banking and financial transactions. The banking system in India is basically divided into organized and unorganized sectors. Commercial banks, cooperative banks, development banks and regional rural banks make up the organized sector. Moneylenders and indigenous bankers belong to the unorganized sector.

Electronic Banking in the Indian Banking Sector

Electronic banking or e-banking is often considered to be the most important invention in banking. Electronic banking is a collective term for the direct sale of banking goods and services to customers via electronic channels. Banks offer their customers their goods and services through electronic distribution channels. The main delivery channels include ATMs, telephone banking, internet banking and mobile banking. It is a system that automatically provides services to consumers 24 hours a day, seven days a week, regardless of their geographic location. E-banking enables consumers to carry out financial transactions from the comfort of their own home or workplace using an internet-connected PC or laptop. Today, all banks, whether public or private, promote e-banking at their locations. This is simply because

e-banking enables banks to increase their revenue by lowering various operational costs related to the banking corporation. Kurtas (2005) estimates that the average cost of a direct financial transaction over the Internet is \$0.010. Unlike ATM transactions, which cost \$0.27, phone transactions cost \$0.54 and physical branch transactions cost \$1.07. E-banking eliminates the need for paper transactions and goes to great lengths to enable more echo-friendly banking. E-banking services are very creative and of exceptional quality. In summary, e-banking offers several advantages to banks, which is why banks are taking significant steps to promote it (Kurtas, 2000)

Literature of Review

(Sabastian Titus A.P and Albin D. Robert Lawrence, 2003), E-Banking Internet banking is a payment system that allows banks and financial institutions to conduct financial and non-financial transactions over the Internet. The banking system is also sometimes referred to as e-banking or internet banking. This service gives customers access to almost all banking functions previously only available in a local branch, including financial transfers, deposits and online bill payment. Anyone who has registered with a bank for online banking or who has an active bank account or other account is eligible to use the Internet Banking Service. Examples of e-banking are mobile banking, smart cards, internet banking and electronic money transfer systems. E-banking offers a range of benefits including reduced transaction costs, improved customer relationship management and the elimination of geographic boundaries. Customers

use e-banking services from their homes, saving them time and money by eliminating the need to go to the bank's office. Customer Satisfaction Consumer satisfaction is a critical factor in the process of evaluating purchasing, spending, or product or service usage experiences and therefore plays a crucial role in long-term consumer responses. Due to increased competition and recent advances in technology, happiness has received more attention in the banking industry as well. Because of the similarity in the banking sectors' salable goods and services, numerous customer satisfaction efforts have been made to explain customer differentiation and choice in terms of service satisfaction.

(Wurster, V. and Thomas, S, 2015) ,in their article Changes in Retail Banking, the retail banking strategy of the past two decades, which fueled branch expansion, was driven by factors that no longer apply. The author found that liberalization and technological advances are disrupting the competitive balance that used to allow small and large industries to coexist because their overall cost positions were comparable. The reasons for this shift are as follows: (1) consumers are more willing to forgo the convenience of local branches in exchange for higher rates from a distant institution; (2) interest rate deregulation has eroded banks' funding cost advantage over non-banks; and (3) local banks and non-banks have turned competition into a process of exploiting differences in product costs, distribution costs, and the opportunity to obtain higher prices. Competitive advantages in banking will certainly take two forms in the future: (1) strong customer relationships as the basis for selling a diverse range of goods or (2) a low cost position. The banks' strategy must be fully integrated with the requirements of their individual consumer categories.

(Deepjyoti Choudhury, 2015), emphasized that mankind has made countless advances in science, medicine and technology over the past two centuries. Adaptation to technology can be seen everywhere, from the giant spaceship to the tiny handheld smartphone. Dependence on such technologies has become established and is considered the fourth pillar of life alongside air, water and food. No industry in the modern age of technological change is immune to the use of information systems, and banking is no exception. Banks are looking for new ways to offer and differentiate their diverse range of services. Business and retail customers are no longer willing to queue at banks or wait in queue for the most basic services. Electronic banking services, whether offered online or otherwise, have spread rapidly around the world in recent years. The aim of this research is to evaluate the available literature and to determine the characteristics and attitudes of bank customers towards electronic banking (e-banking) delivery channels. In the course of the literature review, some socio-economic and demographic

characteristics of bank customers related to the adoption and use of electronic banking were discovered. The aim of the study was to identify research gaps. Finally, the study sheds light on the current positive association between e-banking satisfaction and word of mouth, as well as the beneficial role that e-banking delivery channels play in fostering loyalty.

(Srinivasa Rao, 2014) tried to show the prospects and future role of retail banking in India. Retail banking is widely recognized as an important factor in a country's economic development. Retail banking is contributing to the growth of the Indian banking sector by offering a variety of new services. It is estimated that retail lending accounted for about one-fifth of total bank lending. In recent years, the real estate market has seen an increase in credit availability. The retail credit market has changed dramatically from a seller's market to a buyer's market. Gone are the days when getting a personal loan was difficult. All the above claims demonstrate the rapid growth of retail banking in India. Retail banking is a broad term that includes commercial banks' transactions with individual customers, both on the liabilities and the assets side. On the asset side, mortgages and loans (e.g. personal/residential real estate, vehicles and educational institutions) are the main items provided by banks. Credit cards and banking services are examples of related ancillary services.

(Rabia Najaf, Khakan Najaf, 2014) examined the importance of e-banking in Pakistan. In the banking industry, e-banking is an important sector. E-banking has brought about very big changes in the Pakistani banking system. The potential for e-banking in poor and underdeveloped countries lies in the cheap cost and time savings, as demonstrated by the use of primary data in this study. The basic data was analyzed in order to collect customer perceptions of electronic banking products. In addition, the research aimed to examine the impact of electronic banking in Pakistan and the performance of electronic banking. Every person's life is influenced by technology these days. Electronic banking is gaining popularity around the globe and many nations including Pakistan are using this technology. They shared their insights into the impact of strategic activities on information technology and the role of perceived risk. The study concludes that by using the internet, users can access their accounts from anywhere. In addition, it was found that almost 90% of the population in Pakistan uses e-banking technology.

Scope of the Study

This research mainly deals with the services offered by banks in India. E-banking is an additional source of income for banks. Banking services help banks to expand their ancillary

businesses. It is primarily aimed at people, employees, families, students and entrepreneurs. It used customer relationship management to build a solid customer base. The aim of this survey was to determine consumers' knowledge, perceptions, opinions and satisfaction with the banking services offered by banks.

Need in support of the study

Banks are crucial to a country's economic prosperity. In today's world, the banking sector is vital to many service industries. Their ability to make a positive contribution to kick-starting a development process depends heavily on how banking policies are pursued and how the financial system is organised. In India in particular, a whole series of banks entered the Indian markets in the course of globalization. Although private banking sectors are controlled by their ability to offer competitive services, public sector banks are inevitable in India. The private customer business is based on the principle of customer satisfaction.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the perception of the customer towards E-Banking Services
2. To study the level of Satisfaction of Customers on E-Banking Service of Banks

Research Methodology

220 respondents were identified to measure customer satisfaction related to the adoption of technology-enabled banking self-services using the survey methodology. Customer perceptions of technology-enabled banking self-services offered by their bankers are considered for the study. The ranking technique is used to determine the level of satisfaction.

Customer satisfaction related to the adoption of technology-enabled banking self-services

In India, the banking industry has promoted economic growth and ushered in a new era of prosperity. Self-service banking is becoming increasingly popular in India and around the world. Customers can now make bank deposits, transfer money, pay bills, and perform other business transactions with banking self-services. It bridges the gap between depositors and borrowers by increasing customer satisfaction, raising awareness and improving service quality for banking self-services. Customers' views on new innovative technologies have evolved in the Indian banking industry. The aim of this study was to assess customer attitudes and satisfaction with technology-enabled banking self-service. According to the survey, customers

of banking services are more aware and satisfied with their financial institutions' banking products and services.

Graph No.1

The banking industry has undergone several changes as a result of the Indian government's new economic policies focused on privatization, globalization and liberalization. In today's banking world, the customer is king. Today, customer service preferences and expectations are evolving at a rapid pace. The goal of bankers is to enable consumers to achieve their goals easily and happily. Customers are generally satisfied with the banks' service quality. In addition, the factor analysis determined the customer's perception, awareness and satisfaction with self-services.

Use of Internet Banking Service

The researcher attempted to examine respondents' experiences of online banking in this area. The researcher collected information on the number of years the researcher used online banking, the frequency with which the researcher used internet banking, and the sources from which the researcher accessed internet banking.

Graph No.2

Years of using internet banking facility

From the chart above, it can be seen that the majority of respondents (36%) used internet banking for a period of 6 months to 1 year, while only (18%) of the respondents used internet banking for more than 5 years. The other segments include less than 6 months (14%), 1-3 years (15%) and 3-5 years (17%) of respondents.

Customer perceptions toward of technology-enabled banking self-services offered by their bankers

The researcher analysed customers' perceptions of technology-enabled banking self-services by their bankers. Through the reliability analysis, the researcher has identified the factors associated with the preference for technology-enabled banking self-services.

Table No.1

Sr. No	Factors	Mean	Std.Deviation
1	Provides efficient services	2.71	2.44
2	Provides accurate information	2.32	2.09
3	Anywhere banking facilities	2.64	2.37
4	Convenient accessibility	3.09	2.37
5	Convenient location of ATMs	2.50	2.30
6	Reputation of the bank	3.00	2.70
7	Lot of facilities provided by e-channels	2.54	2.29
8	Online shopping	2.46	2.30
9	Security/less risk to use	2.48	2.23
10	Savings in Time	2.53	2.25
11	Online bill payment	2.36	2.04
12	checking balance online	2.32	1.98

13	E- Ticketing	2.34	2.00
14	Download previous bank transaction history and Statements	2.35	2.02
15	Applying for customer loan	2.45	2.17

Table 1 shows the result of the descriptive statistics. Convenient accessibility (3.09) is found as a technology. Enabled Banking Self Services Bank reputation (3.00), Provides efficient services (2.71), Banking facilities everywhere (2.64) and Saving time (2.53) are also found highly enabled banking services. It is understood that most respondents have similar opinions on other factors. But the ranking based on the mean and standard deviation is shown in Table 2 below.

Table No.2

Sr. No	Factors	Mean Rank
1	Provides efficient services	5.42
2	Provides accurate information	4.64
3	Anywhere banking facilities	5.27
4	Convenient accessibility	6.18
5	Convenient location of ATMs	5.00
6	Reputation of the bank	6.00
7	Lot of facilities provided by e-channels	5.07
8	Online shopping	4.93
9	Security/less risk to use	4.96
10	Savings in Time	5.05
11	Online bill payment	4.73
12	checking balance online	4.64
13	E- Ticketing	4.67
14	Download previous bank transaction history and Statements	4.69
15	Applying for customer loan	4.91

Chart No.3
Customers' Perception towards Technology Enabled Banking Self Services offered by their Bankers

Based on the mean and standard deviation, the mean rank shows the rank of convenient accessibility (6.18), bank reputation (6.00), provision of efficient services (5.42), and bank facilities everywhere (5.27) in first place according to the perception of the respondents.

Conclusion

Innovative features are critical to the success of any business or institution. It plays a crucial role in the banking sector by developing innovative products for financial transactions. There will be a financial viability of the offer for both the bank and the customer. Banks should become more customer-centric, offering a wide range of online banking products and services through a variety of delivery channels to meet the ever-changing needs and desires of their customers. As the financial market becomes more competitive, banks need to grow to provide the sector with up-to-date and sophisticated services. It is proposed that banks will be encouraged to develop and market novel online banking solutions to meet the ever-changing demands of consumers.

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